

INDIA AND MILLENNIUM DEVELOPMENT GOALS

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Abstract:

The millennium declaration adopted by the general assembly of the United Nations in September 2000 reaffirmed its commitment to achieve universal primary education, promote gender equality and empower women, improve maternal health, reduce child mortality, combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and TB, ensure environmental sustainability, and global partnership for development. The frame work has been contextualized for India. The 12th Five Year Plan (2012-2017) goal is to achieve “Faster, More Inclusive and Sustainable Growth” which is in conformity with the MDGs. The paper analyse the progress of India towards millennium development goals. India’s achievement in respect of the MDGs is a mixed bag. For some indicators India is fast, that is, it has already achieved the target level well ahead of the dead line, like halving the percentage of population below the poverty line. In respect of some indicators, India is expected to reach close to the target level by 2015 if not actually meet the target level like ratio of girls to boys in primary and secondary education and tertiary education, at primary level this target has been met already, at the secondary level; India will be close to achieving gender parity by 2015, but at the tertiary level it is unlikely to achieve gender parity by 2015. India is unlikely to reach the targeted level of 109 per 100,000 live births by 2015. The areas of concern are the rest of the indicators especially those relating to share of women in wage employment in the non- agricultural sector, proportion of seats held by women in National Parliament, proportion of population with access to improved sanitation, urban and rural. In respect of these indicators India is lagging behind by a huge margin.

Key words: millennium, HIV/AIDS, secondary education and tertiary education, Development, Goals.

INTRODUCTION:

The millennium declaration adopted by the general assembly of the United Nations in September 2000 reaffirmed its commitment to the right to development, security and gender equality, eradication of myriad dimensions of poverty, improved health etc. The millennium Declaration adopted eight millennium development goals (MDGs), which are:

- MDG 1: Eradicate Extreme Poverty and Hunger
- MDG 2: Achieve Universal Primary Education
- MDG 3: Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women
- MDG 4: Reduce Child Mortality
- MDG 5: Improve Maternal Health
- MDG 6: Combat HIV/AIDS, Malaria and TB
- MDG 7: Ensure Environmental Sustainability
- MDG 8: Develop Global Partnership for Development

MDG 1: Eradicate Extreme Poverty and Hunger

Target 1: To reduce the proportion of people whose income is less than one dollar a day to half between 1990 and 2015.

Indicators

1. Poverty Headcount Ratio (percentage of population below the national poverty line)
2. Poverty Gap ratio
3. Share of poorest quintile in national consumption

Target 2: To reduce the proportion of people who suffer from hunger to half between 1990 and 2015.

Indicator

4. Prevalence of underweight children under three years of age.

MDG 2: Achieve Universal Primary Education

Target 3: Ensure that, by 2015, children everywhere, boys and girls alike, will be able to complete a full course of primary schooling.

Indicators

5. Net Enrolment Ratio in primary education
6. Proportion of pupils starting Grade 1 who reach Grade 5
7. Literacy rate of 15-24 year olds

MDG 3: Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women

Target 4: Eliminate gender disparity in primary and secondary education, preferably by 2005, and in all levels of education not later than 2015.

Indicators

8. Ratio of girls to boys in primary, secondary and tertiary education
9. Ratio of literate women to men, 15-24 years old
10. Share of women in wage employment in the non- agricultural sector
11. Proportion of seats held by women in National Parliament.

MDG 4: Reduce Child Mortality

Target 5: Reduce by two-thirds, between 1990 and 2015, the Under-Five Mortality Rate Moderately

Indicators

12. Under- Five Mortality Rate
13. Infant Mortality Rate
14. Proportion of one year old children immunised against measles

MDG 5: Improve Maternal Health

Target 6: Reduce maternal mortality ratio by three quarters between 1990 and 2015.

Indicators:

15. Maternal Mortality Ratio
16. Proportion of births attended by skilled health personnel

MDG 6: Combat Hiv/Aids, Malaria and Other Diseases

Target 7: Have halted by 2015 and begun to reverse the spread of HIV/AIDS

Indicators

17. HIV prevalence among pregnant women aged 15-24 years
18. Condom use rate of the contraceptive prevalence rate

19. Condom use at last high risk sex
20. Percentage of population aged 15-24 years with comprehensive correct knowledge of HIV/AIDS

Target 8: Have halted by 2015 and begun to reverse the incidence of malaria and other major diseases.

Indicators

21. Prevalence and death rates associated with Malaria
22. Proportion of population in Malaria risk areas using effective Malaria prevention and treatment measures (Percentage of population covered under use of residuary spray in high risk areas)
23. Prevalence and death rates associated with Tuberculosis
24. Proportion of Tuberculosis cases detected and cured under DOTS

MDG 7: Ensure Environmental Sustainability

Target 9: Integrate the principle of sustainable development into country policies and programmes and reverse the loss of environmental resources.

Indicators

25. Proportion of land area covered by forest
26. Ratio of area protected to maintain biological diversity to surface area
27. Energy use per unit of GDP(Rupee)
28. Carbon Dioxide emission per capita and consumption of Ozone -depleting Chlorofluoro Carbons (ODP tons)
29. Proportion of the Households using solid fuels

Target 10: Halve, by 2015, the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation.

Indicators

30. Proportion of population with sustainable access to an improved water source, urban and rural
31. Proportion of population with access to improved sanitation, urban and rural

Target 11: By 2020, to achieve a significant improvement in the lives of at least 100 million slum dwellers.

Indicators

32. Slum population as percentage of urban population

MDG 8: Develop A Global Partnership For Development

Target 18: In cooperation with the private sector, make available the benefits of new technologies, especially information and communications.

Indicators

33. Telephone lines and cellular subscribers per 100 population
34. Internet subscribers per 100 population
35. Personal computers per 100 population

The frame work has been contextualized for India. All the 8 Millennium Development Goals, 12 of the 18 targets, namely target 1 to target 11 and target 18 are relevant for India. These 12 targets and 35 indicators under the 8 Goals constitute the instrument for statistical tracking of the MDGs in India. The paper analyse the progress of India towards millennium development goals.

India's millennium development goals (MDGs) framework is based on the 2003 United Nations Development Goals (UNDGs) guidelines on concepts, definition and methodology of MDGs indicators. This framework recognizes 53 indicators (48 basic and 5 alternatives). But the 2003 UNDG framework for MDGs is not followed in toto. The frame work has been contextualized for India. All the 8 Millennium Development Goals, 12 of the 18 targets, namely target 1 to target 11 and target 18 are relevant for India. These 12 targets and 35 indicators under the 8 Goals constitute the instrument for statistical tracking of the MDGs in India.

MDGs have helped in bringing a much needed focus and pressure on basic development issues, which in turn led the governments at national and sub national levels to do better planning and implement more intensive policies and programmes. In India the various development programmes / schemes are formulated and implemented under the Five year Plans (FYP). The 12th Five Year Plan (2012-2017) goal is to achieve "Faster, More Inclusive and Sustainable Growth" which is in conformity with the MDGs.

The 12th Plan has identified 25 core indicators, which reflect the vision of faster, sustainable and more inclusive growth and some of the indicators of 12th Plan are more stringent than the MDGs. The 12th Plan aims to reduce the Poverty Head Count Ratio (PHCR) by 10 percentage points over the preceding estimates by the end of 12th Plan, that is PHR to be reduced to 11.9 per cent by 2017, the corresponding MDG indicator is to reduce PHR to 20.74 per cent by 2015. The 12th Plan aims to reduce under-nutrition among children aged 0-3 years to half of the NFHS -3 level (that is from 40 per cent to 20 per cent) by the end of 12th Plan, which means by 2017. The corresponding MDG indicator is to reduce prevalence of under nutrition among children below 3 years to 26 per cent by 2015. The 12th plan envisages reducing infant mortality rate (IMR) to 25 per 1,000 live births, and reducing maternal mortality rate (MMR) to 100 per 100,000 live births by 2017, the corresponding MDG indicators are to reduce IMR to 27 per 1,000 live births and to reduce MMR to 109 per 100,000 live births by 2015.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

MDG 1: Eradicate Extreme Poverty and Hunger

Poverty has always been a cause of great concern for India as it is home to 1.2 billion people, which is 17 per cent of the world population. However, as the Statistics reveals, over the years, all-India Poverty Head Count Ratio (PHCR - percentage below the national poverty line) has declined by 15 percentage points from 37.2 per cent in 2004-05 to 21.9 per cent in 2011-12. During this period rural poverty head count ratio declined by 16 percentage points from 41.8 per cent to 25.7 per cent and urban poverty declined by 12 percentage points from 25.7 per cent to 13.7 per cent. With a faster decline in PHCR i.e annual decline of 1.9 percentage points during 2004-12, compared to 0.7 percentage points during 1993-2004, the country has already achieved the MDG target, which is a notable achievement.

The persisting wide gap in rural-urban poverty ratio (i.e., 21 per cent in 2011-12) is a cause of concern. In all states, except Punjab (Rural: 7.66 per cent, Urban: 9.24 per cent), rural poverty ratio was higher and the rural – urban gap in PHCR varied from 1 percentage point to 29 percentage points.

Though the states have performed better over the years in reducing poverty, in 2011-12, the states of Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Assam, Odisha, Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Jharkhand and Chattisgarh have PHCR above the national level estimate of 21.9 per cent.

Proportion of under-weight children below 3 years during 1990 was 52 per cent. To meet millennium development goal target, India is required to reduce it to 26 per cent by 2015. By 2015, India is likely to reduce it to 33 per cent, which is slow or almost off track of millennium development goal.

The Government of India has taken a number of initiatives towards eradicating poverty and hunger as poverty remains to be the major hurdle towards sustainable development in the Country. These are as follows:

National Food Security Mission (NFSM): The NFSM objectives are increasing production of rice, wheat and pulses through area expansion and productivity enhancement in a sustainable manner in the identified districts of the country, restoring soil fertility and productivity at the individual farm level, creation of employment opportunities, and enhancing farm level economy (i.e. farm profits) to restore confidence amongst the farmers.

Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY): This is a central assistance scheme. The purpose of this programme was to encourage states to draw up District and State agricultural plans and also increase their own spending on the sector so as to reorient agricultural development strategies for rejuvenating Indian agriculture during the Eleventh Plan (2007–12). RKVY is preferred by States for its inbuilt flexibility in selecting interventions and setting State specific targets. During the Twelfth Plan RKVY will need to be reoriented to facilitate such market reforms, higher expenditure on SAUs and for infrastructure development, besides emphasising effective formulation and implementation of District Agriculture Plans.(XII Plan, Vol.II: 48-49). Promoting agriculture is imperative for meeting the Millennium Development Goal of halving poverty and hunger by 2015 and continuing to reduce poverty and hunger for several decades thereafter (World Development Report).

Rural Development Programmes: Rural Development Programmes cover employment through the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act and the National Rural Livelihoods Mission, housing via the Indira Awaas Yojana and other State schemes and bank support, sanitation through the Total Sanitation Campaign, provision of drinking water via the National Rural Drinking Water Programme, social security through the National Social Assistance Programme, watershed development via the Integrated Watershed Management Programme (XII Plan, Vol.II: 286) and fighting malnutrition among children below 6 years of age and pregnant women and lactating mothers via the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Scheme

MDG 2: Achieve Universal Primary Education

Net enrolment ratio in primary grade was 77 per cent in 1990. To meet target of millennium development goal, it is required to bring it to 100 per cent by 2015. India is likely to achieve it by 2015 because during 2010-11, net enrolment ration in primary grade was 99.89. In 2013, 96.8 per cent of all 6-14 year old children in rural India are enrolled in schools with the proportion not enrolled falling marginally, from 3.5 per cent in 2012 to 3.3 per cent in 2013. The proportion of girls in the age group 11 to 14 not enrolled in school dropped from 6 per cent in 2012 to 5.5 per cent in 2013. Private school enrolment of 6-14 year olds has risen steadily from 18.7 per cent in 2006 to 29.0 per cent in 2013 (Economic Survey 2013-14: 245).

The focus of Saakshar Bharat (SB)/ Adult Education is female literacy. While only 73 per cent literacy has been achieved as per Census 2011, there is marked improvement in female literacy. Male literacy at 80.89 per cent is still higher than female literacy at 64.64 per cent but the latter increased by 10.9 percentage points compared to the 5.6 percentage points for the former. By the end of March 2013, the programme was sanctioned in 1.61 lakh gram panchayats of 383 low female literacy districts in 25 states and 1 UT. Over 1.52 lakh adult education centres have been set up, manned by 2.42 lakh village coordinators. Up to August 2013 about 24.37 million learners, of which around three-fourths are women, have successfully passed the assessment tests for basic literacy conducted by the National Institute of Open Schooling. Nearly 2 million adults have been skilled in various vocational trades by jan shikshan sansthans.

MDG 3: Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women

In recognizing the importance of education in gender equality and empowerment of women, the very first indicator of MDG 3 is to monitor the status of girls' enrolment in Primary, Secondary and Tertiary levels of education.

Gender Parity Index (GPI) in enrolment at primary, secondary and tertiary levels is the ratio of the number of female students enrolled at primary, secondary and tertiary levels in public and private schools to the number of male students. To standardise the effects of the population structure of the appropriate age groups, the GPI of the Gross Enrolment ratio (GER) for each level of education is used, i.e. $GPI (GER) = GER (Female)/GER (Male)$. A GPI of 1 indicates parity between the sexes or no gender disparity. A GPI that varies between 0 and 1 typically means a disparity in favour of males whereas a GPI greater than 1 indicates a disparity in favour of females (See Table 1 Gender Parity Index)

Table 1: Gender Parity Index (Gross Enrolment Ratio) – All India

	1990-91	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11
Primary Education	0.76	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.98	1.00	1.00	1.01
Secondary Education	0.60	0.79	0.80	0.82	0.85	0.85	0.88	0.88
Tertiary Education	0.54	0.71	0.69	0.69	0.70	0.70	0.74	0.86

Source: Millennium Development Goals India Country Report 2014.

The Table 1 shows that in primary education, the GPI of GER has gone up from 0.76 in 1990-91 to 1.01 in 2010-11 showing 33 per cent increase, in secondary education the increase is from 0.60 in 1990-91 to 0.88 in 2010-11 thereby showing 47 per cent increase, and in higher education, it is increased from 0.54 in 1990-91 to 0.86 in 2010-11 registering an increase of 59 per cent.

MDG 4: Reduce Child Mortality

The infant mortality rate (IMR) is another dimension of human capability where we are making progress. IMR fell from 80 in 1991 to 66 in 2001 and at a faster rate thereafter to 47 in 2010. The rate of decline was 14 in the first period and 19 in the second period. Nevertheless, the level of IMR remains high and we need to do much better for our children. We must strive to bring the IMR down to 28 by the end of the Twelfth Plan (XII Plan, Vol.I:10).

State-wise data on human development indicators 7 display considerable variation in performance across States. Kerala was the best performer, witnessing a literacy rate of 93.91 per cent, sex ratio of 1,084 and infant mortality rate of 12 per thousand. At the other end of the spectrum, the worst performance on these indicators was displayed by Bihar (lowest literacy rate of 63.82 per cent), Haryana (sex ratio of 877) and Madhya Pradesh (IMR of 67). Importantly, the BIMARU States, despite witnessing impressive growth rates, continued to remain at the bottom of the distribution in terms of performance on human development indicators. However, the richer States too were not immune from poor performance on these indicators. The below-average performance of Haryana and Punjab, two of India's richest States, on indicators such as sex ratio and female literacy rates points to the inadequacy of per capita income in measuring the economic and social progress in society (XII Plan, Vol.I:308).

Under five mortality rate per 1000 live births was 126 in 1990. It is required to reduce it to 42 per thousand live births to meet millennium development goal by 2015. Latest status shows that by 2012 it was 52. Hence, millennium development goal (i.e., 42 per 1000 live births) is likely to be achieved by 2015.

MDG 5: Improve Maternal Health

Maternal death is an important indicator of the reach of effective clinical health services to the poor, and is in turn act as one of the composite measure to assess the country's progress. The Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) is the number of women who die from any cause related to or aggravated by pregnancy or its management (excluding accidental or incidental causes) during pregnancy and childbirth or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy,

irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, per 100,000 live births. (Millennium Development Goals India Country Report, 2014:78).

The percentage of women giving birth in institutions with the benefit of skilled birth attendants has increased from 53 per cent in 2005 to 73 per cent in 2009. We need to do even better, and the Twelfth Plan must bring MMR down to 1 per 1,000 by the end of the Plan period (XII Plan, Vol.I:10). The decline in MMR during 2004-06 to 2007-09 was 5.8 per cent per year (that is, 254 to 212) is well short of the Eleventh Plan goal of 100. Besides Kerala (81), two more States namely Tamil Nadu (97) and Maharashtra (104) have realised MDG target of 109 in 2007–09, while Andhra Pradesh (134), West Bengal (145), Gujarat (148) and Haryana (153) are in closer proximity. The worst performance was found in Assam (381), Bihar (305), Jharkhand (278), MP (310), Chhattisgarh (275), Odisha (277), Rajasthan (331), Uttar Pradesh (345) and Uttarakhand (188) (XII Plan, Vol.III: 03).

Maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births in 1990 was 437 and it is required to bring it down to 109 to meet millennium development goals by 2015. During 2010-12 it was 178. By 2015 it is likely to achieve 139 MMR per 100,000 live births. Hence, in respect of MMR, performance of India is slow or off-track.

MDG 6: Combat HIV/AIDS, Malaria and TB

Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS) have the potential to undermine the massive improvements that have been made in global health over the years. Apart from being a serious health problem, the multi layered effects of the epidemic on the socio-economic fabric of whole nations, makes HIV and AIDS a potential development threat worldwide. Against a target to halt and reverse the HIV/ AIDS epidemic in India, there has been a reduction of new HIV infections in the country by 57 per cent. Still, an estimated 20.9 lakh people were living with HIV/AIDS in 2011. The programme includes Targeted Interventions focused on High Risk Groups and Bridge populations, Link Workers Scheme, Integrated Counselling and Testing Services, Community Care, Support and Treatment Centres, Information, Education, and Communication and condom promotion (XII Plan, Vol.III: 07). In this respect target is trend reversal and performance of India is on track as trend reversal in HIV prevalence has achieved.

MDG 7: Ensure Environmental Sustainability

Many of the greatest challenges to humanity in the future will relate to the effects of global environmental changes – in climate, urbanization, water availability, and loss of biological diversity. In this respect target is trend reversal and not based on base year value. Government of India is focussing on promotion of green business: an environment has to be created wherein being green is not viewed as just an obligatory expectation of a company, but as an area of primary focus for the company to be developed further and be recognised as a leader. Protecting natural resources: natural resources have to be prolonged to their fullest use to maintain the aim for continual economic growth and lessen environmental impacts. Addressing funding issues: which act as a constraint for movement towards a more sustainable industrial model (XII Plan, Vol. II: 77).

MDG 8: Develop Global Partnership for Development

In this respect millennium development Target is increasing trend and not based on base year value. The telecommunications sector has witnessed phenomenal growth during the last decade. Growth of mobile telephony has been the most visible indicator and catalyst to economic growth. The Indian telecom network with 903.09 million telephone connections, including 873.36 million wireless telephone connections, at the end of June 2013 is second largest network in the world after China. Out of this, 357.61 million telephone connections are in rural areas and 545.48 million are in urban areas of the country. A worrying feature, however, has been the slow growth in broadband penetration and usage. Broadband subscription was only about 14 million in March 2012, much below what is needed. The growth of world-class telecommunication infrastructure in the country has been driven by

proactive policy initiatives (XII Plan, Vol. II: 258). The National Telecom Policy (NTP)-1999 recognised that access to telecommunications is of utmost importance for achieving the social and economic goals and help in addressing the developmental challenges of the country.

CONCLUSION

Coming to India's achievement in respect of the MDGs, it is a mixed bag. For some indicators India is fast, that is, it has already achieved the target level well ahead of the dead line, like halving the percentage of population below the poverty line. Target 7 and Target 8, which are of the trend reversal type have also been realized as India has successfully halted the spread of HIV/ AIDS and reversed the spread of HIV/ AIDS. India has halted spread of Malaria and TB and has ensured reversal of spread of Malaria and TB. In respect of some indicators, India is expected to reach close to the target level by 2015 if not actually meet the target level like ratio of girls to boys in primary and secondary education and tertiary education, at primary level this target has been met already, at the secondary level; India will be close to achieving gender parity by 2015, but at the tertiary level it is unlikely to achieve gender parity by 2015. In case of reducing by two-thirds the Under Five Mortality Rate (U5MR), U5MR is estimated at 52 per 000' live births in 2012. To meet the target, India has to reduce it to 42 per 000' live births by 2015. Keeping in mind the sharp decline in U5MR witnessed during the last few years (annual reduction by 3 percentage points during the last 3-4 years) India is expected to reach very close to the target level by 2015. In the extremely crucial field of 'improving maternal health' between 1990 and 2015 India is supposed to reduce by three quarters the Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR). This is a substantial improvement from an estimated MMR level of 437 per 100, 000 live births in 1990-91. But India is unlikely to reach the targeted level of 109 per 100,000 live births by 2015. The areas of concern are the rest of the indicators especially those relating to share of women in wage employment in the non- agricultural sector, proportion of seats held by women in National Parliament, proportion of population with access to improved sanitation, urban and rural. In respect of these indicators India is lagging behind by a huge margin.

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